

Supplemental Information for:

Whole-genome sequencing illuminates multifaceted targets of selection to humic substances in Eurasian perch

Mikhail Ozerov, Kristina Noreikiene, Siim Kahar, Magnus Huss, Ari Huusko, Toomas Kõiv, Margot Sepp, María López, Anna Gårdmark, Riho Gross, Anti Vasemägi

Table of Contents:

Fig. S1. Box-plots showing the level of dissolved organic matter content (DOC) and water color (ln-transformed) and lake size (area and shoreline distance, ln-transformed) between humic and clear-water lakes.	Page 2
Fig. S2. (a) Box-plot showing the level of observed heterozygosity (H_o) between perch samples from humic and clear-water lakes. Dot plots showing the relationships between observed heterozygosity and (b) DOC, (c) water color, (d) area, and (e) shoreline length estimates (ln-transformed) in each lake.	Page 3
Fig. S3. PCA summarizing the genetic structure for 256,880 intergenic SNPs.	Page 4
Fig. S4. (a-d) Genetic divergence (δ) between humic and clear-water perch in the genomic regions containing visual opsin genes.	Page 5

Fig. S1. Box-plots showing the level of dissolved organic matter content (DOC) and water color (ln-transformed) and lake size (area and shoreline distance, ln-transformed) between humic and clear-water lakes (P -values of non-parametric Mann-Whitney test are presented). Horizontal line, rectangle, and whiskers indicate the median, 25th and 75th quartiles, and the non-outlier range, respectively.

Fig. S2. (a) Box-plot showing the level of observed heterozygosity (H_o) between perch samples from humic and clear-water lakes (non-parametric Mann-Whitney test $P = 0.11$). Horizontal line, rectangle, and whiskers indicate the median, 25th and 75th quartiles, and the non-outlier range, respectively. Dot plots showing the relationships between observed heterozygosity and (b) DOC, (c) water color, (d) area, and (e) shoreline length estimates (\ln -transformed) in each lake. Humic and clear-water populations are indicated as black- and white-filled points, respectively. The country of origin is depicted by different point shapes as shown in the legend.

Fig. S3. PCA summarizing the genetic structure for 256,880 intergenic SNPs. Humic and clear-water populations are indicated as black- and white-filled points, respectively. The country of origin is depicted by different point shapes as shown in the legend.

Fig. S4. (a-d) Genetic divergence (δ) between humic and clear-water perch in the genomic regions containing visual opsin genes. Candidate SNPs, non-synonymous candidate SNPs and other SNPs are shown as red, black and grey dots, respectively. Moving average of δ and H_0 of humic and clear-water perch across 50 SNPs are shown as black, brown and cyan solid lines, respectively. Gene symbols are presented as human (and zebrafish for opsins) orthologues and perch GenBank gene IDs (PFLUV_G) for genes with unidentified functions. Opsin genes are highlighted in black. Dashed line shows δ threshold = 0.268, which corresponds to 2.5 SD of mean δ .